

Hybrid Framework for GDPR Data Compliance

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***Abstract:** European Union General Data Protection Regulation came into effect in 2018 bringing significant changes and new requirements for the parties involved in the data sharing process. GDPR defines several actors of that process, and understanding the relationship and interaction points between them is a crucial element in ensuring and maintaining compliance. We will argue that the commonly accepted techniques are either encumbered by extensive use of proprietary technologies or very specific in focus; targeting industrial use in the former case or academic and specialist use in the latter. The goal of current research is to obtain a standardised, trackable, and compliance enabling solution, understood and implemented by various audiences; from data managers to academics and legal personnel. Aiming for the solution to potentially become a standard in itself, it is imperative that it should utilise technologies that are transparent by design and based on standards published and maintained by widely recognized Standard Setting Organizations (SSO) or Standards Development Organizations (SDO), in this case, trusted Consortia W3C and OMG.*

1 Introduction

The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (**GDPR**) (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2016) came into effect in 2018 bringing a plethora of changes and requirements on the parties involved in the data sharing process. GDPR expands on existing European regulations and specifies many additional rules, rights and obligations on all parties. GDPR also defines several actors in the data sharing process, and understanding the relationship and interaction points between them is a crucial element in ensuring and maintaining compliance. GDPR introduces several data subject's rights in addition and with support of the data controller's duties or obligations. Data controllers have to be legally and technologically prepared to respond to a multitude of different scenarios when handling and operating the data.

We will argue that the current state of the art allows for improvement when we consider the data sharing between the parties as defined by GDPR; especially from an interoperability point of view. The techniques currently used are either encumbered by extensive use of proprietary technologies or very specific in focus; targeting industrial use in the former case or academic and specialist use in the latter. The goal of current research is to obtain a standardised, trackable, and compliance enabling solution that can be understood and implemented by various audiences; from data managers to academics, and legal personnel. Aiming for the solution to potentially become a standard in itself, it is imperative that it should utilise technologies that are transparent by design and based on standards published and maintained by widely recognized Standard Setting Organizations (SSO) or Standards Development Organizations (SDO), in this case, trusted Consortia W3C and OMG.

Emerging from the scope of this paper, and the underlying research, are the standard security techniques which would have to be used in an actual production implementation of the proposed solution. The described solution encodes and preserves privacy and GDPR compliance, as long as it is orthogonally provided via standard security measures, such as identity and entitlement management, encryption in rest and transfer, etc.

We will firstly define relevant concepts; data sharing, transparency and open data following which we will examine open data technologies and business process modelling. What will follow is a more definite list of requirements, underscored by such concepts. Subsequently, we will propose a hybrid solution which follows best practices and open standards while catering to the needs of diverse audiences.

2 Data Sharing Concepts

2.1 Data Sharing

Data sharing is defined as the disclosure of data from one organisation to a third-party organisation(s), or the sharing of data between different parts of an organisation (Information Commissioner's Office, 2019). Data sharing agreement (DSA) exists as a tool to regulate the data sharing process and define obligations and constraints on all parties involved. DSA should be detailed enough to address most common scenarios, when it comes to actual data exchange and workflows associated with it. It also needs to comply with the latest legal regulations. Such agreement is, in effect, a *contract* between all parties and should needed, can be amended.

A *smart contract* can be defined as an agreement whose execution is automated. At a very basic level, this assumes an absence of human intervention. Although such contracts can be technologically implemented in various ways, there is still a lot of ambiguity when it comes to their legal merit (Raskin, 2017). The rise of blockchain technology gave this term a new meaning, with many attempts to technologically formalise such contracts. The efforts vary from open-source Ethereum (Ethereum Foundation, n.d.) with its scripting language Solidity to new industrial efforts such as DAML (Digital Asset Holdings, LLC, n.d.).

2.2 Transparency

We understand **transparency** as an “open, comprehensive and understandable presentation of information” (ISO/IEC, 2021). Indeed, within GDPR, transparency has a key role and the data controller is required to “take appropriate measures” (Art. 12-1) to ensure it is applied to the data sharing process. Data subjects have a right to know, at any given time, where their data is being used, for what purpose, how and with what other parties it is shared.

All the mentioned requirements and duties imposed on data controllers also need to be propagated to other data controllers and data processors that would receive such data, referred to as third parties in GDPR. In the form of duties and obligations, under GDPR, they become an institutional responsibility under a named data controller. An accountability mechanism needs to be in place to ensure that other data controllers have followed all the original data requests (and data controller) sourced directly from the data subject, propagating the requests to all third parties. Most importantly, there has to be a clear track record, presented in a transparent manner for all the parties to review, if needed.

2.3 Open data

Open data is the concept or general notion which we define as data freely available for everyone to use (and republish), without copyrights and patent restrictions commonly associated with proprietary data. The importance of open data has been long recognised in all areas, from the public sector (Data Protection Commission, 2016), to industry (Manyika et al., 2013), making its way into the national Open Data Strategy (Government Reform Unit, 2017). Although usually associated with the web, in the form of the web of open data (Auer et al., 2007), it is not exclusively tied to it.

2.4 Interoperability in Terms of GDPR

GDPR defines personal data as “information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person”, whom it refers to as a data subject (Art. 4-1). It further clearly defines two other actors in the data sharing process, namely a data controller and data processor. Data controller “determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data” (Art. 4-7) while the data processor “processes personal data on behalf of the controller” (Art. 4-8). Other (legal) person, agency or body receiving the data for the purpose of further processing is defined as “third party” and acting “under the direct authority of the controller or processor” (Art. 4-10). That could be another data controller or processor not directly involved in the original agreement between the data subject and the data controller.

Finally, in Art. 51(1) GDPR defines another actor not directly involved in the data sharing process per se, but it rather supervises the data sharing process; namely Supervisory Authority. While each EU Member State assigned it, it is defined as “independent public authority” responsible for monitoring the conformance to GDPR, in order to “protect the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons concerning processing and to facilitate the free flow of personal data within the Union”. When it comes to data rights and obligations, defining relations between all actors is at the core of GDPR and essential in generating legally compliant data sharing agreements.

The issue of interoperability in terms of GDPR is driven by the complexity of the relations between GDPR-defined actors. By understanding their relationship and then defining the interoperability points, we build a base for our modelling approach. The model identifies generic actor functions that the IT system could implement, but that would have specific obligations placed upon them in achieving GDPR compliance. The framework model we developed, identified potential interoperability reference points between those functions, as targets for the definition of interoperability protocols and interoperable data exchange formats. The Figure 1 outlines how the different provisions of GDPR place requirements upon these interoperability reference points. The Figure 2 build on the preceding outline, illustrating the subset of the Interoperability Reference Model involved in use cases around the GDPR compliance, satisfying Data Subject (DS) requests between parties of a DSA. We derive our requirements from a framework for system interoperability for systems seeking system solutions for GDPR compliance (Pandit et al., 2018).

Figure 1: Interoperability Reference Model for GDPR compliant systems

Figure 2: Boundary of DSA problem scope against the GDPR Interoperability Reference Model from (Pandit et al., 2018)

We assume the data being shared is from a primary Data Controller (DC) that received the data directly from the Data Subject and that will be the recipient of any requests to serve GDPR rights from the data subject. The other party in the DSA is termed the Third Party (TP). In terms of GDPR, that could be either another Data Controller or a Data Processor (DP), and in terms of our analysis, we do not distinguish between these roles as far as serving Data Subject request implications on the relationship that is subject to the DSA. For this paper, we do not address some of the interoperability reference points that would be implicated in these scenarios (shown as dotted lines in Figure 2). Specifically, we do not address the reference points where the Data Subject interacts with the Supervisory Authority (SA), with the Data Controller’s Data Management Function (DM) or directly with the Third Party. We also do not address the reference point that allows the Third Party acting as a Data Controller to manage GDPR implication of data sharing with fourth parties and beyond. Though we anticipate the interoperability

solution applied to the other reference point in this paper would apply to the unaddressed reference points, we do not attempt to explore this claim further in this paper.

3 Open Data Technologies

3.1 Semantic Web

The semantic web is a concept conceived at the turn of the century in response to the ever-growing issue of data management, more specifically knowledge modelling (W3C, 2015). In short, it is a web of data, the web behind the scenes, designed to be readable by both humans and machines by following certain standards. We can have that data linked to and from other data and describe that concept as Linked Data (LD); the idea is to have all the data presented to follow certain paradigms and rules. Over the years, many techniques emerged to keep that data organised in a logical and structured fashion, resulting in multiple Semantic Web Ontologies (SWO), practically vocabularies of different concepts within a particular namespace. There are ontologies describing datasets, legal concepts, relationships, provenance and many more.

This information is represented via RDF (Resource Description Framework); the information is displayed by using semantic triples consisting of a subject, predicate, and object. Each item in the triple is expressed as a Web URI (Uniform Resource Identifier). There are multiple ways to output such information by the means of serialisation. The most popular ways to serialise RDF are RDF/XML, Turtle, N-Triples, JSON-LD and more. For this paper, we use XML serialisation as explained later in the text.

3.1.1 Semantic Web Ontologies

The semantic web draws its main strength from the sheer number of ontologies it uses. That flexibility enables many applications over a wide area of different interests. We mention a few that are directly relevant to our model.

Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) (Iannella, 2004) is in essence a Rights Expression Language (REL). ODRL is intended to provide and declare open machine-readable rights policies but can be used as a machine-readable format to define various data protection conditions in a process of data sharing or exchange. The ODRL Core Vocabulary (Iannella et al., 2018) defines the semantics for the concepts and terms from the ODRL Information Model (Iannella & Villata, 2018). It is based around *Policy* (a group of one or more Rules), *Rule*, *Action* (operation on an Asset), *Permission* (to exercise an Action over an Asset), *Prohibition* (to exercise an Action over an Asset), *Duty* (obligation to exercise an agreed Action), *Asset* (resource or a collection of resources that are the subject of a Rule), *Party* (entity or a collection of entities that undertake Roles in a Rule) and *Constraint*. ODRL allows for the creation of custom profiles that are used for defining more specific actions and classes, catering for both basic and advanced implementations.

Data Protection Rights Language (DPRL) (Hadziselimovic et al., 2017) is, in essence, an ODRL profile that expands ODRL actions to be more in line with data protection regulations, specifically GDPR, by extending its core vocabulary. Although ODRL has certain relevant action concepts defined in its vocabulary, for data protection, actions to track the implementation of data subject rights are key to ODRL being useful in GDPR compliance. In other words, in some instances, ODRL needs to fully map to proper GDPR legal terminology; for example, actions *read* and *inform* can be expressed in

single-action *dprl:access* that directly maps to GDPR definition of a corresponding data subject right. In other instances, there are no ODRL equivalents for required actions. Therefore, DPRL introduces the following actions/concepts: *dprl:access*, *dprl:rectify*, *dprl:erase*, *dprl:port*, *dprl:restrict*, *dprl:object*, all in response to GDPR defined data subject rights. This is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Modelling DPRL Actions based on GDPR terms and ODRL Actions

Data Subject Rights in GDPR	Related ODRL Actions	DPRL Corresponding Action
Right to information	Inform, Read	Inform
Right of subject access	Inform	Access
Right to rectification	Modify	Rectify
Right to erasure	Delete, Uninstall	Erase
Right to remove the consent	Obtain Consent	RemoveConsent
Right to data portability	Move, Sharing, Transform	Port
Right to restrict access	Give, Grant Use, Review Policy	Restrict
Right to object to procedure	-	Object

Linked Data Platform (LDP) (Speicher et al., 2015) is a standard interface for accessing Linked Data. LDP defines a set of rules for HTTP operations on web resources, some based on RDF, to provide an architecture for read-write Linked Data on the web. Built upon the idea of RESTful services, LDP uses similar HTTP verbs and methods, namely, POST, GET, PUT, PATCH and DELETE to facilitate CRUD operations on data resources, while aiming to adhere to standards applicable to industry implementations (Mihindikulasooriya et al., 2013).

DataID Core ontology (Freudenberg & Brümmer, 2016), an extension to the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) (Maali F. et al., 2014), defines concepts and properties to describe simple and complex datasets in an interoperable way. It adds features such as dataset hierarchies, permissions, distribution and machine-readable licensing information. DataID integrates provenance information from the PROV Ontology enabling the tracking of the provenance of the datasets, but also including versioning and inter-dataset relationship information. The main motivation behind DataID is to enhance DCAT’s provenance information and to further explain the relations between the datasets, with a concept of data distribution as an instance of original data.

Dataset Usage Vocabulary (DUV) (Farias Lóscio et al., 2016) is specifically used in tracking, sharing, and persisting dataset usage. It follows best practices for the data on the web, providing descriptive metadata that provides insights to the consumer about how published datasets can be used. It can keep a consistent record of dataset sharing between the parties.

SHACL – Shapes Constraint Language (Knublauch & Kontokostas, 2017) – is a language for validating RDF graphs against a set of conditions. These conditions are provided as shapes and other constructs expressed in the form of an RDF graph. RDF graphs that are used in this manner are called “shapes graphs” and the RDF graphs that are validated against a shapes graph are called “data graphs”. Such a process produces another type of graph, namely a validation graph that effectively summarises the results of the validation. SHACL is a necessary addition to RDF technology to be able to express cardinalities of components as common in other modelling systems.

3.2 XML

The Extensible Markup Language (XML) (Bray et al., 1998) is a subset of SGML (Connolly, 1995), a standard for defining generalized markup languages. The main purpose of this language is to enable generic SGML to be “served, received, and processed on the Web in the way that is possible with HTML” (Bray et al., 1998). It was originally designed for interoperability with both SGML and HTML, but over time it became a synonym for storing and transporting data on the web. Due to the extensibility hinted in its name, it can be used as a general-purpose metalanguage for operations directly on data itself, providing a convenient way for both structuring and querying the data sources. It is also a common ground for the technologies used in our modelling approach, namely linked data serialisation, validation and process modelling.

3.2.1 XML Data Structure

XML from a structural point of view is just a piece of information wrapped in specific tags, very similar to HTML (Henke, 2009). Tags (also referred to as elements) can be used to describe the entities but could also carry metadata in the form of attributes for further structuring and definition. XML can define more advanced concepts, such as namespaces, enabling further structuring, targeting or ignoring purpose-specific data, and avoiding potential name conflicts among elements and attributes from various areas and vocabularies.

The concept of namespaces (denoted by *xmlns*) opens up several possibilities, such as using XML Schema¹; successor of DTDs (document type definition), often referred to by the initialism for XML Schema instances, XSD (XML Schema Definition). XSDs are far more powerful than DTDs in describing XML languages. They use a rich data-typing system and allow for more detailed constraints on an XML document's logical structure. XSDs also use an XML-based format, which makes it possible to use ordinary XML tools to process them. Another valuable application of namespaces is seen with the XSL namespace² that enables transformations (XSLT) of the document into different formats such as HTML. XSLT comes with many elements that can be applied to the XML code, such as *if*, *for-each*, *include* and many more, enabling structural and conditional logic to decide the output produced. Apart from XSLT, another important extension to XML is XPATH, providing navigation around the XML tree and using criteria to select the elements.

XML Schema provides means to statically validate XML documents, mostly in terms of syntax and structure. If we want to assess the business logic, we need an additional tool in our toolbox. For such purpose, we use **Schematron**, a rule-based validation language for making assertions about the presence or absence of patterns in XML trees. Schematron schema makes assertions applied to a specific context within the document. If the assertion fails, a diagnostic message is supplied. Schematron relies on XPath and uses regex-like patterns to define rules within a certain context using assertions to specify the constraints that should be checked within that context.

In other words; by using Schematron, we will be able to assess if our specific use case model follows certain rules in terms of syntax, logic in terms of flow, and respects the given constraints. The core component of the modelling part is a dynamic validation with Schematron. Using XPath expressions, Schematron is capable of, not just defining the constraints and syntax, but also the logic behind the business model. In other words, it

¹ *xmlns:xs="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema"*

² *xmlns:xsl="http://www.w3.org/1999/XSL/Transform"*

can show whether the process of executing DPRL actions in parts of our business model reaches its logical ending and if it was compliant with every step of the process.

3.3 Business Process Modelling

A **business process** is a combination of a set of activities within an enterprise with a structure describing their logical order and dependence whose objective is to produce the desired result (Aguilar-Savén, 2004). New GDPR rules force organisations to reshape the way they approach the management of personal data stored and exchanged during the execution of their everyday business processes (Agostinelli et al., 2019).

Business Process Model And Notation (BPMN) explains the business process following convenient and easy to understand graphical notation and symbols without the unnecessary overhead that other approaches might have. It is easy to comprehend even without detailed prior knowledge of how the process modelling works in terms of business logic. Such readability creates a base for streamlined processes that can be easily controlled by Data Controllers, processed by Data Processors, and assessed by Supervisory Authorities. In other words, our model will be effectively simple at the top, and sufficiently detailed at the bottom.

BPMN is practically a standard for process and workflow modelling. Using BPMN for legal compliance had been discussed but usually limited to generic compliance (Geiger et al., 2017) or used as a tool for visualising specific GDPR use cases (Agostinelli et al., 2019). In our case, BPMN serves as an integral part of our model, not just as a visualisation tool, but as a base for running dynamic validity or compliance checks. Moreover, running BPMN processes can be set up (and it is a best practice to do so in enterprise applications) to create an auditable electronic trail that proves chain of custody integrity (a major challenge with digital assets).

4 Requirements Analysis

For our modelling, as mentioned previously, we focus on open web data technologies and utilise several semantic web ontologies serialised as XML. The reason we choose XML is that it is a common denominator when it comes to semantic web ontologies serialisation, schema definitions, and storing the BPMN graphical notation. This exposes artefacts from all parts of our modelling exercise to existing robust XML tooling and validation methods.

We currently restrict our data model to this specific set of rights mentioned in the previous part, due to being directly relevant to data sharing agreements. In the following, we are looking in detail at the rectification use case, rather than analysing each case individually. “Rectify” is a GDPR action verb that needs to be added to any ODRL specialisation that aims to address the GDPR use cases. Rectification is a special case of modification in terms of compliant agent actions. Modification, unlike reading or indeed writing is a true acid test of interoperability when assessing compliance of agents. The task is to change data, preserve the integrity thereof, and not compromise privacy or security in the process. The right of the protected consumer to get their personal data rectified is one of the core features of GDPR based protection. Thus, the Data Controller must be capable of handling the rectification requests properly.

As a prerequisite for rectification, the affected consumer needs to be able to inspect their personal and personally identifiable data held by the Data Controller. So, each rectification case begins with a request to create and present (publish, but just to the

affected end-user) a small relevant data set that needs to be presentable in the human-readable form to the relevant consumers and only them. The consumer can request to fix any erroneous entries including deletion, if appropriate. Typically, the rectification requests should be granted unless there are statutory reasons not to. For instance, merchants are required to store transaction data for certain period of time as outlined by national regulation.

Rectification request can be considered as an umbrella case for all other GDPR-defined data subject rights. Our main focus is the relationship between the data controller and data subject in terms of sharing the data sharing with third parties as defined in the data-sharing agreement. Therefore, when we look at the individual scenarios in terms of data subject rights mentioned above, we take this into account in resolving the exact set of the requirements. We derive our requirements based on the lifecycle of the data and what level of access is required by a data subject. It is summarised in the CRUD matrix in Table 2 where every GDPR action should be *initialised* by the data subject (C), potentially *accessed* (R), *modified* (U) or *erased* (D).

Table 2: Level of data manipulation needed by individual GDPR actions

DS actions in GDPR	Initialise (C)	Access (R)	Modify (U)	Erase (D)
Inform	Y	Y	N	N
Subject access	Y	Y	N	N
Rectify	Y	Y	Y	Y
Erase	Y	N	Y	Y
Remove the consent	Y	Y	N	N
Port	Y	Y	N	Y
Restrict access	Y	Y	N	N

Based on the above and driven by the interoperability points depicted earlier in Figure 1 and Figure 2, we derive our requirements.

First, data sharing parties should be able to exchange data and metadata needed to respond to data subject requests related to their GDPR rights. It should be done in a way that can be reused and familiar to both parties across different instances of data sharing and for different data processing applications.

Second, both data sharing parties can record their actions and interaction in responding to data subject requests related to their GDPR rights in a way that can be examined by internal data protection officers and supervisory authorities, in assessing GDPR compliance of these actions.

Lastly, the design of the process followed across both parties in response to data subject requests related to their GDPR rights should be clearly documented and understandable by both parties and their data protection and operational staff.

Consequently, we present our full requirements diagram with three main top-level requirements: legal compliance, transparency and interoperability. For legal compliance, our model should be auditable and be able to produce some kind of contract. Using open-source and open standards, together with auditability also satisfies our transparency requirement. Finally, to satisfy the interoperability model (Figure 1 and 2), we split our interoperability requirements into *syntactic*, *semantic* and *behavioural* interoperability

components. For the illustrative purpose, we can look at the part separating our interoperability and in relation to the technologies (depicted in grey boxes) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Requirements - interoperability³

Figure 4: UML package diagram of the technologies used

³ Full resolution images available at: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/5092544>

The technologies used and their domain of application is more closely depicted in the package diagram in Figure 4. The diagram shows two main aspects of our data model when it comes to the technologies used in our data protection open contract: semantic web technologies and XML technologies. Although they are interlinked in a way that semantic web does use XML (among other technologies) to serialise its output; but in terms of technological aspect, they are in separate packages.

5 Hybrid Approach to Compliance Tracking

There are currently other tools used in compliance checking, some of them even using Semantic Web Technologies and they serve their purpose in various scenarios. We argue that existing solutions may assess some aspects in compliance checking, but often do not leverage the simplicity and practicality that can be offered with Semantic Web Technologies in conjunction with BPMN modelling and the abundance of robust tooling available when all of that serialised as XML. The hybrid approach we introduce has three main benefits over similar solutions:

- It is easy to follow by Data Controllers and Processors;
- It is easily accessible in its graphical representation to both legal personnel and data managers;
- Common standards-based format and validation methods streamline the role of the Supervisory Authority.

We also argue that current practice lacks clear guidelines and requires enhancement, which is easily achieved through the transparency of open data standards and the extensibility and flexibility offered by SWO. Our approach fills those gaps by not adhering to one specific technology, but by using an open and transparent approach to create a robust, traceable, and verifiable model to serve the implementation of such a contract. Similarly, the approach is not limited to automated contracts, but rather it focuses on an open, on-demand contract which can be assessed and understood regardless of the current state of the system.

5.1 Interoperability Framework

To produce an open data protection contract or DSA model which will maintain GDPR compliance, we rely on the technologies introduced previously. Rather than focusing on defining a smart contract between the parties, we produce an on-demand open contract using a 2-way API defined by LDP to initiate compliance checking. It revolves around the concept of triggers; processes initiated by Data Subjects' requests, while following certain rules in pursuit of legal compliance. In such a process, we focus on three aspects: interoperability, flexibility, and transparency. As shown previously, we define interoperability points first, while we address the flexibility through a variety of semantic web ontologies (and their extensions) and the transparency through open linked data standards.

We introduce a hybrid modelling approach: using BPMN at the process level and UML at lower levels in conjunction with the aforementioned semantic web technologies. We define our modelling structure by separating practical use cases into categories and further sub-categorising based on the aspects they assume. This structure is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Categorisation of use cases

BPMN helps visualise this process by showing the pool (modelling canvass) representing the request as a whole, with swim lanes (sections of the canvass representing actors in a process) representing data sharing actors (in the case shown in the partial diagram in Figure 6, it is DS, DC and TP). Circle shapes define events such as triggers, endpoints, message exchange. Rectangular, rounded-cornered shapes represent tasks and diamond shapes are specific gateways (parallel, inclusive, and exclusive). Finally, the arrows represent sequence flow and can be incoming or outgoing. The interoperability points between the actors, can easily be visualised, as the lines of sequence flow cross the boundaries of swim lanes. We can also track the request and assess different scenarios following through various gateways. Any BPMN diagram can be serialised as XML, with the *bpmn* namespace separated into three distinct parts - *bpmn:collaboration*, *bpmn:process* and *bpmndi:BPMNDiagram*. We can see how such a diagram can be used in the aforementioned *rectify* case.

Figure 6: Partial view of BPMN⁴

⁴ Full resolution images available at: <https://zenodo.org/deposit/5092544>

In essence, we can visualise our model through the use of BPMN, with specific elements relating to previously defined components. To understand these components better across different domains and how different technologies can work together, we approach the issue using *separation of concerns*.

6 Separation of Concerns: Bringing Different Technologies Together

The hybrid model brings different technologies together, semantic web ontologies, business process modelling, data exchange and validation standards. We try to consolidate them; although they have several things in common, they also use different approaches, methodologies, and terms.

Separation of concerns is a method that first uniquely identifies each technology; secondly looks at the terms and concepts it is using; finally brings them together by finding the appropriate common denominator or common ground. In other words, the method finds the commonalities and then uses consistent wording between different domains. This could be probably easier to explain by looking at Table 3, where we define four main components (in terms of their domain) or entities of our model: Message, Decision, Action and Flow.

Table 3: Separation of concerns by domain

DPRL Entities	BPMN	ODRL	Schematron
Message	Event	Action	Element body
Decision	Gateway	Rule	Rule
Action	Task	Action	Assert/Report
Flow	Flow	Asset \Rightarrow Relation	Pattern

In the BPMN world, messages are *events*, they can be defined either as *triggers* or *reactions* to other events. As far as ODRL is concerned, they translate into *Actions*, a native ODRL concept. Decisions are *gateways* in BPMN, we utilise *inclusive* and *parallel* decisions, or *rules* in ODRL. For Schematron goes as a schema language, the mapping is done through the predefined concepts that can be applied to the elements; element body is applied to our message, rule to a decision and so on. Schematron is fairly simple in that aspect, yet powerful.

To summarise, there is a concept of *messages* that can be *triggers* or *reactions*; *decisions* that can be *inclusive* or *parallel*; *actions* that can be in response to a message or in response to decision making; *flows* connect other elements or define directions of decisions. This separation lets us dissect the model and its components more thoroughly and present the role that each of them plays in our hybrid model.

6.1 Technical Analysis

Our model, as discussed previously, uses XML as a way to serialise and define the structure and schema. By using semantic web vocabularies, we define our components, their relationship, an action to be performed, and a set of constraints. On the other hand; using Schematron. we apply business logic to our process model presented in BPMN and thus dynamically validate the flow.

6.1.1 DPRL Components

We define the components of our model based on the previous observations and requirements introduced previously. Based on ODRL defined classes, each component is either *odrl:Party*, *odrl:Asset* or *odrl:Agreement*. They are defined through the DPRL ontology and for quick reference, we also individually list them here.

odrl:Party sub-classes: *DataSubject*, *DataController*, *DataProcessor*, *DataManager*, *ThirdParty*, *SupervisoryAuthority*.

odrl:Agreement sub-classes: *DataSharingAgreement*.

odrl:Asset sub-classes: *DataAsset*.

The relationship between the components described above is also defined through DPRL, using *odrl:assigneeOf* property when it comes to the relationship between Party components. Other components, like Agreement and Asset, have their relationship defined through *odrl:relation* property. Actions performed between the components are included in the *odrl:Action* class and are listed here individually. They correspond to GDPR defined actions analysed earlier: *dpml:inform*, *dpml:modify*, *dpml:erase*, *dpml:removeConsent*, *dpml:port*, *dpml:restrict*, *dpml:object*.

To define constraints in our data model in terms of semantic web defined properties, we use SHACL as well as ODRL's built-in constraint property. SHACL constraints are used to define Party properties in terms of cardinality, but also to define the data types. An example is in Listing 1.

```
ex:DSShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  sh:targetNode dpml:DataSubject ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path dpml:id;
    sh:name "Data Subject" ;
    sh:description "Data Subject unique identifier" ;
    sh:datatype xsd:string ;
    sh:maxCount 3 ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
  ] ,
  sh:property [
    sh:path dpml:DataSubject ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ; ] .
```

Listing 1: SHACL defined constraints

On the other side, ODRL constraints can apply to permissions, prohibitions and obligations defined by that ontology. The example below (Listing 2) sets temporal constraints, giving party-specific permission that expires on a specific date.

```
odrl:permission [{
  odrl:target "http://example.com/document:1234" ;
  odrl:assigner "http://example.com/org:616" ;
  odrl:action distribute ;
  odrl:constraint [{
    odrl:leftOperand xsd:datetime,
    odrl:operator odrl:lt,
    odrl:rightOperand { "@value": "2021-01-01", "@type": "xsd:date" }
  }]
}] ;
```

Listing 2: ODRL defined constraints

6.1.2 BPMN Diagram

In previous paragraphs, we have demonstrated that semantic web technologies can be used to define components of our model, their relationship and actions performed. We also presented how to set several constraints in terms of data shapes and allowed actions to be performed. Although semantic web with its ontologies is very versatile in defining all the aspects of a data model, relations and actions, it lacks in business process applications. Linked data and semantic web technologies present a solid conceptual ground. Nevertheless, using a hybrid approach by defining the process itself in BPMN and using Schematron for process dependent validation, we can take this model to another level and provide full dynamic validation of the process according to a business logic implied by the requirements of GDPR compliance.

BPMN, as already discussed on a high level earlier, uses a concept of pools (one enclosed system or organisation in a process model) in our case the entirety of a rectify request as implemented in a data controller's system. Each pool can be divided into different lanes, showing individual components of the system; in our case different actors participating in the rectification process.

Looking more closely into the XML backend, there are several parts of the main, all-enclosing *bpmn:definitions* tag that also includes namespaces. First, *bpmn:collaboration* is used for metadata such as description, documentation and participants in the process (not actors as per our swim lanes, but rather concerning BPMN process flow itself). Second, *bpmn:process* defines our pool, lane set and specific lanes with their corresponding nodes (tasks and gateways), but also defines sequence flow (arrows in our diagram) between such nodes. Finally, *bpmndi:BPMNDiagram* helps with an actual graphical presentation by defining coordinates (x, y) of shapes and waypoints, as well as the width and height of particular shapes.

BPMN utilises two main schemas, the first one for the BPMN process, and the other one for the diagram. We will remain within the boundaries set by the schema defined by OMG and introduce other artefacts via XPath and Schematron. The importance of validating whether an XML document conforms to a predefined structure cannot be overemphasized. The idea of interoperability is at the core of XML; one document's output is often input to another document. That input needs to be validated to avoid system-wide errors and ensure the system continues to be operational.

6.1.3 Schematron Validation

Schematron uses the concept of rules, allowing the creation of an arbitrary number of rules, encoding the decision on how strictly any of the rules need to be followed and what messages are produced if any of them are broken. Schematron uses XPath to target those rules within an XML document. XPath follows the root-descendant logic throughout the XML tree, similar to what is used to address assets in hierarchical folders or directories of a file system. For example, the following expression will select *bpmn:process* in our BPMN file:

```
/bpmn:process
```

Attributes can be selected via the "@" sign, so for example, if we want to select lane set id, we would use the following expression:

```
/bpmn:process/bpmn:laneSet/@id
```

Finally, we can filter the results via a predicate, using square brackets to denote it:

```
/bpmn:process/bpmn:laneSet[@id = 'MainLaneSet']
```

We use a similar pattern to create rules in Schematron. We first define the context of the rule by using an XPath expression to define what part of the XML tree the rule applies to. Then we use tags “assert” and “report” to test if the rule should be true. The example below creates a rule within *bpmn:process*, requiring that the lane has an id attribute.

```
<rule context="lane">
  <assert test="@id">The 'lane' element must have an 'id' attribute.
</assert>
</rule>
```

Listing 3: Schematron context and assert example

In the case where this “assert” fails (there is no id attribute on a lane), the validation process will return the text content of the “assert” element. We can use “report” instead of “assert” for the reverse logic (check if the element does not include the attribute instead of checking that the element does include it). The example below is more elaborate, using “assert” tags to check id attributes throughout the document, also performing the uniqueness test. We use the pattern tag for grouping our elements and for readability purposes.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<sch:schema xmlns:sch="http://www.ascc.net/xml/schematron"
  <sch:ns uri="http://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/20100524/MODEL" prefix="bpmn"/>

  <sch:pattern>
    <sch:title>Unique Ids</sch:title>
    <sch:rule context="*[@id]">
      <sch:assert test="not(preceding::*[@id=current()/@id][1])">Id attributes
should be unique in a document.</sch:assert>
    </sch:rule>
  </sch:pattern>

  <sch:pattern name="lane id">
    <sch:rule context="bpmn:lane">
      <sch:assert test="@id">The element lane must have an id
attribute</sch:assert>
    </sch:rule>
  </sch:pattern>

  <sch:pattern name="sequenceFlow id">
    <sch:rule context="bpmn:lane">
      <sch:assert test="@id">The element sequenceFlow must have an id
attribute</sch:assert>
    </sch:rule>
  </sch:pattern>

  <sch:pattern name="id obligatory for other elements">
    <sch:rule
context="bpmn:[@intermediateCatchEvent,@parallelGateway,@exclusiveGateway,@inclusiveGat
eway,@startEvent,@endEvent,@task]">
      <sch:assert test="@id">The element intermediateCatchEvent, parallelGateway,
exclusiveGateway, inclusiveGateway, startEvent, endEvent, task must have an id
attribute</sch:assert>
    </sch:rule>
  </sch:pattern>

  <sch:pattern name="Check source-target constraints">
    <sch:rule context="bpmn:sequenceFlow">
      <sch:assert test="(@sourceRef = '*' and @targetRef = '*') and @sourceRef !=
'">Check the target exists.</sch:assert>
    </sch:rule>
  </sch:pattern>
</sch:schema>
```

Listing 4: Schematron unique id check example

Schematron can further reuse XML Schema conventions to assert if some value is of the proper data type, for example we can constrain our id attribute to be integer only as follows:

```
<assert test="@id castable as xs:integer">
```

The example in Listing 4 shows that Schematron handles static validation easily, possibly overlapping with validation that can be done with XML Schemas, DTDs, RELAX NG and the discussed linked data approach SHACL. However, through the use of Schematron, as we can see, we do not limit ourselves to static validation only. Schematron can do one type of validation where all other mentioned technologies fall short: dynamic validation. One of these scenarios is handling co-constraints (dependency between data within an XML document or across XML documents). By changing certain parts of the schema, we can ensure that the logic of the flow will not be broken, and the model stays validated.

Validation of our BPMN model schema via Schematron is also a novel pursuit. Using a battle-tested approach based on XML gives us not just the transparency but also the robustness that is needed for any compliance check. In summary, Schematron does not define the document's schema (doesn't specify the structure which is provided by other discussed methods) but rather checks throughout the structure of a document if advanced business constraints such as co-occurrence requirements were fulfilled or not. Hence it can be effectively used to express operational and business rules and assertions of the data cardinality (presence or absence of data). It is further able to perform algorithmic checks – determines data validity by performing an algorithm on the data. Because BPMN expresses progression of the static data that needs to be handled in a GDPR compliant way. Static Schematron tests over the BPMN structure effectively become dynamically generated proofs of prescribed chains of custody over digital assets passing through the BPMN defined system.

7 In Conclusion

We have outlined how standardised technologies belonging to different domains can be used to effectively tackle the issue of GDPR compliance. Interoperability and transparency are important concepts that motivate the use of open data technologies to achieve that compliance and satisfy the rules set by GDPR text.

The hybrid approach introduced in this paper is not only a compliance checking tool, but an on-demand open contract tool which can be used by all parties to effectively assess any current or past state of the data sharing process. It also allows the formulation of guarantees that GDPR actions over data passing through a validated BPMN process will preserve GDPR compliance. By using this unique approach, we are addressing the needs of both data managers and legal professionals, as well as consumer data subjects. Finally, each and every technology used has been standardised in trusted consortia (W3C, OMG), making the final solution potentially open for further standardisation efforts. Having a standardised compliance checking tool would be an invaluable contribution to achieving effortless, but systematic in-place compliance checks.

Further work will include side-by-side verification of the Control-Flow Patterns that are implementable in BPMN and could be applied to our model, assessing both Basic Patterns (van der Aalst et al., 2003) and Advanced Branching and Synchronization Patterns (Russell, 2006).

8 References

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